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Incidence of Mycotoxin Contamination along the Maize Value Chain in Lusaka Province of Zambia

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Received Date: 18-Aug-2019

Accepted Date: 27-Aug-2019

Published Date: 29-Aug-2019

Abstract

Aflatoxins and Fumonisin are carcinogenic mycotoxins produced by *Aspergillus* spp. and *Fusarium* spp., respectively that frequently contaminate maize and its derivative products when the conditions are ideal. A survey was conducted to establish levels of aflatoxin and fumonisin contamination in maize and maize products in Lusaka Province of Zambia. Sixty-six maize samples comprising grain, samp, maize flour, and popcorn were collected from farms, markets, street vendor and hammer mills. Total fungal forming units were estimated after plating on selective media and incubating up to 14 days. Quantification of total aflatoxin and fumonisin was done using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. The maize grain sourced from farm stores in Lusaka had highest mean number of fungal colonies, 4.18 ± 0.05 log CFU/g while the breakfast maize mealie meal flour from the supermarkets had lowest number, 1.31 ± 0.11 log CFU/g. All the maize products, tested positive for aflatoxin and fumonisin with 54.6% above the Zambian regulatory standard of $10 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for total aflatoxin, while all the samples were significantly higher than the acceptable level of PMTDI of fumonisin, 2 mg kg^{-1} . Significantly higher amounts of aflatoxins were obtained from hammer mill, $11.28 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ while the least was in the maize products sold by street vendors, $2.62 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. The highest amount of fumonisin was recorded in the maize grain obtained from the farms, 2991 mg kg^{-1} followed by those from the hammer mill, 1659 mg kg^{-1} . Both aflatoxin and fumonisin were found to coexist in all the maize products analyzed. The high levels of contamination observed in the maize products suggest that both the urban and peri-urban population in Lusaka province were being exposed to high levels of both aflatoxin and fumonisin. However, the high level of fumonisin observed in the maize products merits further investigation.

Keywords: aflatoxins, fumonisin, contamination, maize products, Lusaka

Introduction

Maize occupies a central position in Zambia's agricultural political economy as both the national staple food and primary smallholder crop. Maize ear rots caused by *Aspergillus flavus* (Link ex Fr.) and *Fusarium verticillioides* (Sacc.) Nirenberg [syn.: *F. moniliforme*] are the two most important impediments to increased maize (*Zea mays* L.) production in Zambia (Mukanga *et al.*, 2010). Maize ears rot infection results in yield losses and grain quality reduction through discoloured kernels, observed during the grain grading process and production of mycotoxins. These ear rot pathogens are known to produce carcinogenic mycotoxins, Aflatoxins and Fumonisin, in maize (Kachapulula *et al.*, 2017) which pose a serious threat to human and animal food safety (Williams *et al.*, 2004; Probst *et al.*, 2010). High incidence of ear rot infection has been associated with high mycotoxins accumulation in pre-harvest maize in Africa (Bigirwa *et al.*, 2007). It has been postulated that damage caused by ear-feeding pests, favourable pre-harvest and post-harvest conditions and growing susceptible maize varieties promote high ear rot fungal infection and subsequent mycotoxin contamination of grain (Misihairabgwi *et al.*, 2017). The presence of Aflatoxin B₁ in food such as peanuts, milk, and maize is known to increase a person's risk of liver cancer (Wu *et al.*, 2013). In addition, the socio-economic status of majority of inhabitants of sub-Saharan Africa also predisposes humans to consumption of mycotoxin contaminated maize products either directly or at various points in the food chain (Udomkun *et al.*, 2017). The resulting implications include immuno-suppression, impaired growth, various cancers and death depending on the type, period and amount of exposure. A synergistic effect between mycotoxin exposure and some important diseases on the continent such as malaria, kwashiorkor and HIV/AIDS have been suggested (Darwish *et al.*, 2014). Consumption of *F. verticillioides* contaminated maize and a high incidence of human esophageal carcinoma (Rheeder *et al.*, 1992). Fumonisin have been reported to induce several diseases in animals, notably leukoencephalomalacia in horses, pulmonary edema in swine, and liver cancer in human (Antonissen *et al.*, 2014).

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Aflatoxin-related hepatic diseases have also been reported in many Sub-Saharan African countries (Probst, 2010). The well-known fatal mycotoxin contamination occurred in Africa in 2004 and was due to aflatoxins contamination of maize grain and flour (Kimanya *et al.*, 2015).

While outbreaks of ear rot diseases begin in the field, their associated toxins are produced along the maize value chain. According to Hell and Mutegi (2011), the level of mycotoxin contamination of a maize sample depends on the extent of fungal colonization and toxin production at each stage of the value chain. It is thus important that at each stage, the levels of contamination are known. Beside resulting in severe yield losses, mycotoxins reduce crop quality (Munkvold *et al.*, 2003; Nyangi, 2014), where there is poor pre- and post-harvest practices like poor harvesting, processing, and storage which encourage the growth of mycotoxin producing mold (ICRISAT, 2016).

Though very few studies have been carried out to determine the prevalence of these mycotoxins in maize in Zambia (Mukanga *et al.*, 2010), several authors (Bruns, 2003; Hell *et al.*, 2003; Wanjiku, 2015) have reported maize and maize products as excellent substrate for fungal growth and mycotoxin contamination and, co-occurrence of high levels of fumonisins and aflatoxins in maize though in a competitive relationship (Marin, 1998; Robertson-Hoyt *et al.* 2007; Misihairabgwi *et al.*, 2017). A negative correlation has been reported to exist between the growth of *A. flavus* and *F. verticillioides* (Robertson-Hoyt *et al.* 2007) while Abbas *et al.* (2006) found that aflatoxin and fumonisin levels were positively correlated across test environments in maize hybrids naturally infected with both *Fusarium* spp. and *A. flavus* suggesting that both fungi can thrive on similar resources if host plants are highly susceptible. Inevitably, this suggests high exposure of people and animals to these mycotoxins. While the prevalence of fumonisins may be high (Misihairabgwi *et al.*, 2017), no legally advisory limits for various mycotoxins including fumonisins exist in Zambia, the Zambia Standard Bureau regulates aflatoxin B1, the most common form of aflatoxin found in maize, at less than 10 µg kg⁻¹ for human consumption, whereas total fumonisin levels in human food and animal feed are based on the WHO/FAO provisional maximum tolerable daily intake (PMTDI) of 2 mg kg⁻¹ for fumonisins (CAST, 2003).

The most widely used methods for quantifying aflatoxin and fumonisins are the ELISA (Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay), others include TLC (Thin Liquid Chromatography) and HPLC (High Performance Liquid Chromatography) (Guo *et al.*, 2017). The objective of the study was to assess the prevalence of aflatoxins and fumonisins along the maize value chain in three districts in Lusaka province: Chongwe, Kafue and Lusaka.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study site

A survey of farms, markets, hammer mills and street vendors in involved in maize production and trade were carried out in three districts of Lusaka province namely Chongwe, Kafue and Lusaka between August and November 2015 (Figure 1). Lusaka province consists of only 1.4% of Zambia's land area with the larger part being highly urbanized and industrialized. However, the agricultural activities of farmers are mainly in the backyard of the houses or in open spaces in the peri-urban and rural areas of the province. Lusaka province lies in agro-ecological zone II of Zambia, which is characterized by an annual rainfall between 800–1100mm, and the rainy season from October to April while the winter period is from May to July, with mean daily temperatures of 14 -24°C (Table 1).

Figure 1. Location of Chongwe, Kafue and Lusaka in Zambia

Table 1. The Environmental characteristics and population of the study area

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Characteristics	Chongwe	Kafue	Lusaka
Longitude (° E)	28.71	26.2118	28.3228
Latitude (° S)	15.35	15.4515	15.3875
Altitude (metre above sea level)	1069	1008	1277
Annual Rainfall (mm)	813	769	1078.1
Maximum Temperature °C	24.9	21.5	24
Minimum Temperature °C	16.0	14.5	15
Population (as 2017)	137,461	220,695	1,742,979

Study design and sampling strategy

Sixty-six maize samples were collected from 30 farmers, 17 street vendors, 7 hammer mills, and 8 markets (Table 2). From each hammer mill, at least 3 samples were collected over a 2 – 3 days and thoroughly mixed to create a composite sample for milling plant. The samples included 30 maize grain, 2 maize samp, 6 popcorns, and 28 maize flour, i.e., 10 roller meal, 5 Super roller, and 13 Breakfast. Each maize sample was at least 1 – 2.5 kg. In some instance, the samples were purchased from the owners in order to ensure cooperation during the interviews.

Table 2. Distribution of the maize products collected from three districts

Description	Chongwe	Kafue	Lusaka
<i>Source</i>			
Farm	10	10	10
Markets	2	5	4
Street vendors			17
Hammer mill	1	2	5
Total	13	17	36
<i>Type of product</i>			
Grain (kernels)	10	10	10
Maize samp			2
Maize flour		2	3
			5
	3	3	12
Popcorn grain		2	4
Total	13	17	36

Fungal colony count

The quantitative enumeration of fungi as colony-forming units per gram of maize (CFU/g) was performed using the surface-spread method described by Pitt & Hocking (1997). Ten grams (10g) of each sample were grounded and homogenized in 90 ml distilled water solution for 30 min in an orbital shaker. Spore counting was performed by plate count technique on selective media for *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus* (dichloran rose bengal chloranphenicol agar) after incubation for 7 days at 25°C using each suspension in a serial dilution from 10⁻¹ up to 10⁻⁶. The *Aspergillus* fungus appeared as isolated yellow or orange colonies on the plates. All samples were also inoculated onto Nash and Snyder agar (NSA) to enumerate *Fusarium* species (Nelson *et al.*, 1983; Leslie *et al.*, 2006). Nash-Snyder plates were incubated at 24°C for 7 days under a 12 h light/12 h black fluorescent light photoperiod. After incubation, individual counts for each fungal colony recorded, and the results were expressed as total Log CFU per gram of sample.

Sample handling and mycotoxin analysis

Both aflatoxins and fumonisins were analyzed using commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits and protocol (Romer Labs, Inc. SA), the performance of which had been previously validated using the HPLC at Mount Makulu Microbiology Unit (Agilent SA). Total Aflatoxin was extracted from 5-g subsamples of maize flour using 70% methanol and Total Fumonisins (FB1, FB2, and FB3) using 90% methanol. The maize samples were ground in the laboratory in a Romer mill (Romer Labs, Inc.). The solid-phase direct competitive aflatoxin ELISA kit

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consisted of a 96-well microplate coated with an antibody that had been optimized to cross-react with the total aflatoxin and Fumonisins (B1, B2, and B3), respectively. The lower and upper limits of quantification of the test- kit for aflatoxins were 1 and 20 ppb ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), respectively while for Fumonisins were 0.1 and 6 ppm, respectively, according to the manufacturer’s protocol. Optical densities of the reactions for both mycotoxins were quantified using a microplate reader (BioTek Instruments, Inc.) with an absorbance filter of 450 nm. Test values were interpreted with reference to standards that were included in each experiment. Samples with toxin values below the limit of quantification were recorded as containing no detectable toxin. While those with mycotoxin levels above the upper quantification limit were diluted and retested, and the number of mycotoxins was extrapolated from regression lines.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis for survey data was done in Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS). Percentages of samples with detectable aflatoxin (>1 ppb) were estimated. Mycotoxin data were transformed to the logarithm ($X + 1$) and analyzed as a dependent variable in a model in which the factors included in the survey questionnaire served as independent variables. Sources (Farm, market, street vendors and Hammer mills) were modeled as random effects. Results of the analysis were presented as means that were derived by back-transformation of the transformed data. The means and percentages of samples with contamination at different levels were computed for whole grain, maize samp and maize flour collected at the mills.

RESULTS

There were noticeable differences in the number of fungal colony forming units in the different type of maize products collected from different sources (Table 4). Maize samples provided by the street vendors in Lusaka had the highest mean number of fungal colonies (4.11 ± 0.18 log CFU/g), followed by those collected from Hammer mill (4.11 ± 0.01 Log CFU/g). The samples from the open market in Chongwe had the least mean number of fungal colonies (2.14 ± 0.02 Log CFU/g). Among the different types of maize products, the highest number of fungal colonies were isolated from the maize grain from Lusaka ($4.18 + 0.05$ Log Cfu/g), followed by grain from Kafue ($4.11+0.07$ Log Cfu/g). The lowest was in the breakfast mealie meal flour (1.31 ± 0.11 Log Cfu/g). Compared to the maize grain and other products, the breakfast was the finest in texture with pure white colour, the bran and germ are completely probably this created little surface area for colonization by fungal spores.

Table 4. Enumeration of the Fungal Colonies

Description	Fungal colonies (Log CFU/g)		
	Chongwe	Kafue	Lusaka
Source			
Farm	3.45 ± 0.21	3.15 ± 0.05	2.68 ± 0.34
Markets	2.14 ± 0.02	2.45 ± 0.01	3.25 ± 0.31
Street vendors			4.11 ± 0.18
Hammer mill	4.11 ± 0.01	3.56 ± 0.02	3.61 ± 0.02
Type of product			
Grain (kernels)	3.13 ± 0.01	4.11 ± 0.07	4.18 ± 0.05
Maize samp			2.13 ± 0.05
Maize flour	Roller	3.17 ± 0.14	3.12 ± 0.23
	Super roller		3.12 ± 0.01
	Break fast	1.49 ± 0.01	1.65 ± 0.01
Popcorn grain		1.54 ± 0.02	3.32 ± 0.16

Aflatoxin contamination

All the maize samples tested positive for aflatoxins (Table 5). Ninety-eight percent of the maize samples had aflatoxin levels $> 2 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, and 3 (4.5%) had levels $> 25 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and two (3%) more than $50\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. Aflatoxin levels ranged from 2.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ to values as high as 71 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$.

Table 5. Distribution of aflatoxins levels in maize and maize by products collected from three districts.

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District	Number of maize samples contaminated with aflatoxins [n(%)]					
	≤ 2 µg/kg	2 – 10 µg/kg	11-20 µg/kg	21-50 µg/kg	51-100 µg/kg	> 100 µg/kg
Chongwe	0	6 (9.1)	7 (10.6)	0	0	0
Kafue	0	10 (15.2)	7 (10.6)	0	0	0
Lusaka	1 (1.5)	21 (31.8)	9 (13.6)	3 (4.5)	2 (3.1)	0
Total	1 (1.5)	29 (43.9)	23 (34.8)	3 (4.5)	2 (3.1)	0

Apart from Lusaka, no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) were observed among the different sources of the maize products in Kafue and Chongwe. However, the levels of aflatoxins in maize products obtained from different sources were of increasing order: street vendor < farmer < market < Hammer mills (Figure 2). The highest aflatoxin amounts were found in roller meal, 71.0 µg/kg, followed by breakfast meal, 35 µg/kg all from Lusaka, and the lowest was in super roller meal, 2.10µg/kg, also collected from Lusaka. On average, the highest aflatoxin across all maize products was in Lusaka, 8.1µg/kg, followed by Kafue, 3.6µg/kg, and lowest in Chongwe, 3.4 µg/kg.

Figure 2. The levels of aflatoxin contamination in maize samples from the different sources of maize products in the study area

Fumonisin contamination

All the samples tested positive to fumonisins and were above the regulatory 2ppm the WHO provisional maximum tolerable daily intake (FAO/WHO, 2016) (Table 6). More than 93% of the samples that tested positive had more than 10 ppm. The fumonisins ranged from 5 to 8250 ppm. There were relative more samples above greater than 100ppm followed by that above 50ppm than in any of the other five categories.

High levels of fumonisin contamination were recorded in maize grain collected from the farms compared to other stages along the maize value chain (Figure 4). The order of increase in contamination was street vendor < markets < Hammermill < Farm.

Table 6. The levels of aflatoxin contamination in different maize products collected from the three districts

Product	Chongwe	Kafue	Lusaka
	Aflatoxins + SE (µg/kg)		
Maize grain	3.4 ± 0.4	3.2 ± 0.6	3.3 ± 0.4
Breakfast (Super Fine maize flour)	3.3 ± 0.3	5.6 ± 0.4	8.2 ± 5.4

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Super roller (moderate fine maize flour)	-	3.1 ± 0.1	4.6 ± 1.8
Roller meal (Coarse flour)	4.3 ± 0.1	4.9 ± 0.9	15.9 ± 7.4
Maize samp	-	-	3.8 ± 0.6
Popcorn grain	-	2.6 ± 0.4	6.6 ± 0.8
Mean	3.4 ± 0.3	3.6 ± 0.4	8.2 ± 2.3

NB. SE= Standard error

The results in Figure 5, the highest fumonisins amounts were found in maize kernels (2199.9ppm), followed by breakfast meal (1297.5 ppm) all from Lusaka, and the lowest was in popcorn grain collected from Lusaka (127.5ppm)

Table 7. Distribution of fumonisins levels in maize and maize by products collected from three districts.

District	Number of maize samples contaminated with fumonisins ppm [n(%)]10					
	≤ 2ppm	2 – 10 ppm	11 -20ppm	21 – 50ppm	51 – 100 ppm	> 100 ppm
Chongwe	0	1 (1.50)	2 (3.0)	2 (3.0)	5 (7.6)	3 (4.5)
Kafue	0	2 (3.0)	2 (3.0)	2 (3.0)	4 (6.1)	7 (10.6)
Lusaka	0	1 (1.5)	2 (3.0)	10 (15.2)	6 (9.0)	17 (25.8)
Total	0	4 (6.1)	6 (9.0)	14 (21.2)	15(22.7)	27 (40.9)

The significant higher amount of fumonisins were found in the maize products collected from farmers and hammermill (Figure 3). Samples from farmers in Lusaka had the highest contamination, 3374.3 mg/kg followed by those from hammermill in Kafue, 2450mg/kg, and lowest amount was popcorn grain collected from Kafue, 87.5 mg/kg (Table 8). Apart from the maize grain, the other products collected in Lusaka had comparable lower amounts of fumonisins.

Figure 4. The levels of fumonisins contamination in maize-based products from the different sources of maize products in the study area

Table 8. The levels of aflatoxin contamination in different maize products collected from the three districts

Product	Chongwe	Kafue	Lusaka
	Fumonisin + SE (µg/kg)		
Maize grain	1478.7 ± 166.1	1746.9 ± 176.1	3374.3 ± 837.1
Breakfast (Super Fine maize flour)	1297.5 ± 144.5	1958.5 ± 16.5	136.0 ± 14.7

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Super roller (moderate fine maize flour)		1840.0 ± 0.1	610.7 ± 407.3
Roller meal (Coarse flour)	2450.0 ± 0.1	1420.0 ± 180	368.7 ± 162.1
Maize samp			199.5 ± 40.2
Popcorn grain		87.5 ± 22.5	147.5 ± 40.2
Mean	1525.6 ± 149.9	1543.6 ± 171.2	1157.7 ± 328.8

NB. SE= Standard error

DISCUSSION

All the samples collected, though in some cases could have appeared clean, were infected with *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* fungi and, tested positive for the presence of aflatoxins and fumonisins. However, the contamination levels were variable, i.e. higher in some compared to others. Significantly higher amounts of aflatoxins and fumonisins were detected in maize flour (mealie meal) from the hammer mills than another source. The observed variation among different maize flours or mealie meal may have due to the manner in which the product was processed, with the roller meal generally having higher levels of aflatoxins and fumonisins contamination.

Further, the results of the study indicate that more than 90% of the maize products tested had levels of mycotoxins especially fumonisins being higher than the recommended WHO/FAO PMDTI (CAST, 2003) suggesting that they were unsafe for human consumption. It's clear that the aflatoxins and fumonisins contamination was widespread hence the need for remedial measures starting with the source of the grain which is the farm, where thorough cleaning, sorting and grading should be done. This then could be followed by cleaning at the milling plant or hammer mills. Lack of cleaning between successive samples could have contributed to the high levels of aflatoxins and fumonisins observed in maize flour from the hammer-mills. The difference between roller meal and breakfast meal in terms of aflatoxins and fumonisins may be attributed to the removal of bran and germ in latter. Both Park *et al.* (2018) and Nyangi (2014) have reported high levels of aflatoxins and other mycotoxins in the bran and germ, compared to the maize endosperm. The high levels of mycotoxin detected at local mills, markets, and street vendors suggest that these potentially important target points in the maize value chain besides farms for the mitigation efforts. These efforts should include surveillance, education programs to create awareness, introduction of mycotoxin-binding agents and grain sorting (Mutiga *et al.*, 2015). Often, contaminated homegrown maize may enter the maize supply chain by being sold as grain at the market or by street vendors, or as maize flour through the local hammer mill thereby resulting in increased consumer exposure to mycotoxins. At farm level, this exposure is sometimes enhanced by farmers who unknowingly may buy contaminated maize after their homegrown supplies have been exhausted, this is also another potential source of exposure to mycotoxins (Lewis *et al.*, 2005). This has become more apparent with widespread food shortages as a result of drought. It's thus important that various actors in the maize value chain are encouraged to adopt good practices along the maize value chain has been proposed as the best way to reduce levels of fungal toxins in the maize products (Clarke and Fattori, 2013).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Although this study is relatively small targeting only three districts, the results show that most maize products consumed by humans in the peri-urban and urban areas of Lusaka province may be highly contaminated with fumonisins levels higher than WHO/FAO PMTDI of 2 mg kg⁻¹. Most of the previous surveys conducted in Zambia have targeted farm gate maize sample. This survey has extended the understanding further by sampling markets and hammer mill thus capturing the various points along the maize value chain. Even though all maize samples tested positive for aflatoxins, more than 44% of the maize products were within the regulated 10 µg kg⁻¹ thereby making them safe for human consumption. One of the strategies is to improve processing of maize products and continue monitoring and surveillance programs. The higher levels of fumonisins observed in the maize products warrant further investigations. In addition, more sampling exercises are needed to cover the different stages in the maize value chain, including the maize thick porridge consumed by the majority of Zambian and extended the analysis to other mycotoxins.

Conflict of Interest

We declare that we have no conflict of interest

Acknowledgement

I wish to acknowledge the funding of this work by the Strategic Research Fund of National Science and Technology Council of Zambia.

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